

EFFECT OF SHAMANA SNEHA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF ASṚGDARA (ABNORMAL UTERINE BLEEDING): A CASE STUDYSanju*¹, Rajeev Kumar Pandey², Divya Gupta³¹PG Scholar, PG Department of Panchakarma, MMM Government Ayurveda College, Udaipur, Rajasthan India.²Associate Professor, PG Department of Panchakarma, MMM Government Ayurveda College, Udaipur, Rajasthan India.³Lecturer, PG Department of Panchakarma, MMM Government Ayurveda College, Udaipur, Rajasthan India.

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ABSTRACT

Asṛgdara, also known as *Raktapradara*, is a gynecological disorder characterized by excessive and/or prolonged menstrual bleeding. In modern medicine, it is correlated with menorrhagia, defined as cyclic bleeding at normal intervals with excessive volume (>80 ml) or prolonged duration (>7 days), or both. It adversely impacts the physical, social, and psychological well-being of women. The prevalence of abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB) in India is estimated at 17.9%. In *Ayurveda*, *Asṛgdara* is primarily caused by vitiated *Pitta* and *Vata* doṣa, where *Pittaja prakopa* leads to excessive bleeding, and *Vata* contributes to irregularity and pain. This case study evaluates the role of *Shamana Sneha (Yasthimadhu Ghṛta)* along with supportive therapy in the management of *Asṛgdara*. A 28-year-old female presented with complaints of excessive and prolonged per-vaginal bleeding, foul-smelling discharge, and associated pain. After 20 days of treatment, significant improvement was observed in duration, amount of bleeding, pain, and overall quality of life. The results indicate that *shamana Sneha* is effective in controlling excessive bleeding, correcting the doṣic imbalance, and preventing recurrence.

KEYWORDS: *Asṛgdara*, Abnormal Uterine Bleeding, *Shamana Sneha*, *Yasthimadhu Ghṛta*.**INTRODUCTION**

Asṛgdara means *Dirana* i.e. excessive excretion of *Asruk*. Due to *Pradirana* of excessive *Raja* is also termed as *Raktapradara*.^[1] In modern medicine, this condition is correlated with menorrhagia, defined as cyclic menstrual bleeding occurring at normal intervals but with an excessive volume (more than 80 ml) or prolonged duration (over 7 days), or both.^[2] It is a common health concern among women of reproductive age. Excessive menstrual blood loss affects not only physical health but also emotional, social, and psychological well-being. In India, the reported prevalence of abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB) is approximately 17.9%.^[3] This condition can impair reproductive function and, in some cases, necessitate surgical intervention. According to WHO, about 18 million women aged 30–55 years perceive their menstrual bleeding as excessive. *Sodhana* and *Shamana* therapies are advised but if *Rugnabala* is diminished then only *Shamana* is advisable. Acharya Sushruta has said that Prolonged and excessive menstrual bleeding along with Pain and Body ache are the clinical features of *Asṛgdara*.^[4] Since *Asṛgdara* is mainly due to *Vata Pitta Dosh*, *Kashaya Rasa* and *Pittashamaka Chikitsa* may

be adopted. Panchakarma help in breaking down the pathogenesis of *Asṛgdara* and its recurrence.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

To assess the effect of *shamana Sneha* in *Asṛgdara*, specifically in relation to abnormal uterine bleeding.

MATERIALS AND METHODS**Case presentation**

A 28yr old female patient came to panchakarma outpatient department of rajkiya ayurveda Anusandhan kendra, Gulab bagh, Udaipur in 11july 2025with OPD No-16447. Patient came with complaints of Excessive P/V bleeding during menstruation, prolonged bleeding for 1month with interval of 18-20 days. The patient was reportedly in good health until about one years ago, when she suddenly began experiencing excessive per-vaginal bleeding during menstruation. Her cycles occurred every 18–20 days, with excessive bleeding lasting 1month, accompanied by minimal clot formation. She required 5-6 pad changes per day and reported lower abdominal pain along with low backache.

Past history: No H/O DM/HTN/Hypothyroidism or any other major medical or surgical history.

Family history: No history of same illness in any of the family members.

Menstrual History: (unmarried)

Menarche - 12 yrs.

Menstrual cycle: 1 month flow, once in 18-20days

Quantity: excessive bleeding 5-6pads/day

Colour: Dark reddish colour

Odour: Foul smell

Consistency: with clots

Pain: lower abdominal pain, low backache during whole bleeding period

General Examination

Built: Moderate

Nourishment: Moderate

Pulse: 72 b / min

BP: 120/80 mm of Hg

Temperature: 97.4 F

Respiratory Rate: 18 cycles / minute

Height: 150cms

Weight: 65 kg

Ashtavidha Pariksha (eightfold examination)

1.	Nadi(pulse)	Pittja vataj	5.	Shabda(speech)	Sapsta
2.	Mala(stool)	Nirama	6.	Sparsha(skin)	Samshitoshna
3.	Mootra(urine)	Avikrita (pale yellow)	7.	Drika(eyes)	Prakart
4.	Jivha(tongue)	Nirama(uncoated)	8.	Aakriti(posture)	Sama

Dashavidha Pariksha (tenfold examination)

1	Prakriti	Pittja vataj	6	Sara	Madhyama
2	Vikriti	Pittaj	7	Sahanana	Madhyama
3	Pramana	Madhyama	8	Ahara shakti	Uttama
4	Sattava	Uttama	9	Vyayama shakti	Madhyama
5	Satmaya	Madhyama	10	Vaya	Yuvaavastha

Treatment Plan (20 days)

Gokshura Churna^[5] – 5 gm, twice daily after meals

Yoni Prakshalana (Sita Kasaya Kalpana):

Lodhra Churna^[6] – 5 gm

Triphala Churna – 5 gm

Subhra Bhasma – 1 gm

Shamana Sneha^[7]: Yasthimadhu Ghṛta^[8] – 50 ml, once daily before meals with warm water as Anupana.

RESULT

	BT	AT
Menstrual cycle	1 month flow	6-7 days flow
Quantity	excessive bleeding 5-6pads/day	2-3pads/day
Colour	Dark reddish colour	Reddish colour
Odour	Foul smell	No smell
Consistency	with clots	No clots
Pain	Lower abdominal pain, low backache	No lower abdominal pain and backache

DISCUSSION

Asṛgdara is predominantly a Pitta-Vata disorder. Excessive bleeding occurs due to Pitta Prakopa, while Vata contributes to irregularity and pain. Yasthimadhu Ghṛta acts as both Pittashamaka and Vṛṣya, nourishing the uterine tissues and maintaining hormonal balance. Gokshura acts as a Mutrala and Tridoṣasamaka, supporting uterine health. Lodhra, Triphala, and Subhra Bhasma Yoni Prakshalana provide local Stambhana and Shodhana, reducing bleeding and inflammation. Use of Sneha (Yasthimadhu Ghṛta) internally provides Rasayana, Balya, and Stambhana effects, thus breaking the Samprapti of Asṛgdara. The holistic approach of shamana Sneha along with supportive drugs provided significant relief without any adverse effects.

CONCLUSION

The use of Shamana Sneha (Yasthimadhu Ghṛta) in the management of Asṛgdara provided significant

improvement in excessive and prolonged menstrual bleeding, pain, and foul-smelling discharge. The combination of internal Sneha and local Yoni Prakshalana proved effective, safe, and sustainable.

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